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**Negotiating Pakistani English in Education: Teachers' Beliefs
and Classroom Realities**

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Abstract

This research paper deals with the perceptions and challenges associated with Pakistani English. It focuses on the viewpoints, the English Language Teachers of Pakistan possess. As this study is situated within the framework of World Englishes, it addresses the developing identity and acknowledgment of Pakistani English as a recognizable linguistic variety. This study utilizes a mixed-method research design. Thus, it is conducted on quantitative data from Likert scale questionnaires and qualitative perceptions from structured interviews of teachers. The findings expose a general perception among teachers of Pakistani English's discreteness and value. However, there exist an apparent variability in opinions, especially when it comes to concerning its global legitimacy and acceptance. The study also highlights certain challenges that arise while integrating Pakistani English into educational practices. These challenges include its balancing with standardized English forms, adapting relevant teaching materials, and dealing with students' resistance. The research identifies the varying nature of language perception in the context of Pakistan by emphasizing the complex interplay between local language varieties and global language standards. Recommendations of the study include the teacher training, curriculum development, resource creation, and public awareness campaigns to increase the acceptance and integration of Pakistani English in educational settings.

Keywords: Pakistani English, World Englishes, English Language Teachers, Language Perceptions, Linguistic Identity, English Language Teaching (ELT), Language Attitudes

Introduction

The rapid spread of English as a global lingua franca has led the emergence of distinct varieties of English across the world. Each of these varieties are imbued with its own cultural and linguistic idiosyncrasies. Among these linguistic varieties, Pakistani English stands out to be a unique one that is mirroring Pakistan's rich linguistic landscape along with its colonial past. This research delves into the perceptions and challenges that are associated with Pakistani English, with a special focus on the perspective of English Language Teachers in Pakistan. It maps itself out within the

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framework of World Englishes, and aims to unpack the developing and evolving identity and recognition of Pakistani English as a defined and well-founded linguistic variety. By backpacking this under-researched area, the research foregrounds the dynamic nature of language perception in Pakistan, a country where English not only acts as a bridge in global communication but it is also a symbol of socio-economic esteem.

Using a mixed-method approach, quantitative data from Likert scale questionnaires is combined with qualitative insights from structured interviews in this study. The main objective of this research is to disentangle the various views of English Language Teachers on Pakistani English, critically examining its global validity. This whole study is revolving around some core questions. These questions aim at exploring the perceptions of Pakistani English language teachers related to Pakistani English an international variety, challenges they face in its integration into educational setting and how these challenges are pivotal in shaping their perceptions towards this distinct linguistic variant. Thus, an extensive and in-depth understanding of Pakistani English including its curriculum development and its broader recognition in global setting is provided by this research.

Background and Context of the Study

In the past century, the phenomenon, which was unparalleled in the linguistic history, is the widespread of Pakistani English. English being *Lingua Franca*, somehow managed, to cross its linguistic boundaries and spread globally. As there was a widespread of English as *lingua Franca*, thus it led to the rise of many varieties of English which are influenced by the linguistic and cultural background of that specific region in which that variety developed. Among these varieties is Pakistani English, which has the linguistic divergence and cultural legacy of Pakistan.

As Pakistan has a colonial past and a multilingual landscape, so it offers a unique context for the evolution of English. English in Pakistan not only serves as communicative bridges across different linguistic borders but, it also, is taken as a symbol of socio-economic prestige. Thus, version of English that emerged in Pakistan is the result of linguistic, education and linguistic dynamics. Pakistani English, while influenced by British English, has evolved its own distinctive and peculiar attributes, and these attributes played their part in making Pakistani English a distinct variety

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within the spectrum of World Englishes. As the English Language Teachers in Pakistan shape its use and evolution, thus, this study is compelled by the need to explore and understand this unique variety of English from their perspective. Understanding the dynamics of English varieties like Pakistani English, in a globalized world, is important for adequate communication, and cultural reciprocation. This research contributes to knowledge on, “how Pakistani English is perceived and assimilated by Pakistani English language teachers”. It also offers insights that are both academically rich and socially appropriate.

Statement of the Problem

The main problem that is addressed in this study is the current vagueness and challenges that are encompassing the perception and integration of Pakistani English within the domain of language teaching in Pakistan. Within the context of the global spread of English and the rising recognition of differing English varieties, this issue is particularly relevant. The research tries to explore how Pakistani English, as a definite linguistic variety, is perceived by language teachers along with the specific challenges they face in incorporating it into their teaching practices.

The expediency of this research lies in its practical approach, applying both quantitative and qualitative methods to collect a comprehensive data. The relevance of study is highlighted by the aspect that there is a need for a profound understanding of language perceptions in educational domains, specifically in a country where English is an important component of social flexibility and access to global opportunities.

Research Questions

This comprehensive study is guided by following research questions:

1. What are the perceptions of Pakistani English Language teachers towards Pakistani English as an international linguistic variety?
2. What are the challenges that English Language teachers have to face while integrating Pakistani English into their English language teaching practices?
3. How do their overall perception of Pakistani English, as a linguistic variety, is influenced by these challenges?

Research Objectives

The objectives of this study are:

- To delve into the perceptions of Pakistani English Language teachers towards

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Pakistani English as an international linguistic variety.

- To identify the challenges faced by English Language teachers in integrating Pakistani English into their language teaching practices.
- To explore how these challenges may influence the teachers' overall perception of Pakistani English as a linguistic variety.

Significance of the Research

Academic Significance: This research significantly contributes in the academic field of World Englishes by offering data from reliable measurements and observation along with the insights into the perception and integration of Pakistani English. By offering this focused study on a variety that has been relatively underexplored, the existing literature has been enriched, thereby expanding the understanding of the global drift of English.

Social Significance: Socially, the research has deep implications for educational practices and language policy in Pakistan. It offers practical perceptions that can help out in the development of teaching methodologies and materials that are more comprehensive of Pakistani English. These methodologies would enhance the relevance and effectiveness of English language education in the country.

Delimitation of the Research

This research is delimited to the perceptions and experiences of seasoned English Language Teachers of Pakistani universities. Teachers from diverse regions of Pakistan like Karachi, Lahore, Islamabad, Peshawar, and Quetta were chosen for their diverse linguistic and cultural environments. The study excluded the teachers of elementary and secondary levels. A sample of 30 teachers were explored through Likert scale questionnaire while a more focused group of 08 teachers were selected for structured interviews. It especially focuses on these educators' views on Pakistani English and the challenges encountered in integration of Pakistani English in English language teaching. While the findings may have broader implications, the scope of this study is limited to the Pakistani educational context.

Literature Review

The literature review of this research aims at providing an extensive study of the Pakistani English academic discourse. It encompasses its international status, and the challenges encountered in integrating it. In this review, the study is contextualized

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within broader field of World Englishes. The unique position of Pakistani English and the implications for English language education are highlighted as well.

The progression of Pakistani English dates back to the colonial age when English was introduced in the Indian subcontinent by the British colonizers. When Indian subcontinent was divided and Pakistan came into being in 1947, the status of English as a significant language in the newly formed country was still retained. During all these years, Pakistani English managed to develop its own peculiar attributes, making itself a defined variety within the larger domain of world Englishes. Thus, Pakistani English possesses peculiar lexical, phonological, and syntactic attributes which are influenced by the local varieties. As per Baumgardner (1993), the use of sentence patterns and constructions of Pakistani English are influenced by the syntax of local languages. As Pakistani English has its own defined and distinct features and attributes, thus, according to Mahboob (2003), it must be acknowledged as a legitimate variety of English within the domain of World Englishes.

The increasing demand of Pakistani English can also be marked by its recognition in various domains of life such as media, literature and education. Rahman (1990) states that, "Pakistani English is not just a colonial after effect rather it is a productive language which kept evolving over the years and it is used mainly in the Pakistani context.

The framework provided by Barat Kachru (1985) gives a special status to Pakistani English by placing it within the Outer Circle, which according to his "Three Circle Model, consists of countries where English is regarded as second language. However, the oversimplification, which this model provides for the complex dynamics of English, becomes a subject to criticism as Pakistani English is not just a colonization legacy, it is a living entity that keeps on evolving and getting influenced by the linguistic attributes of Pakistan.

The Dynamic Model of Schneider (2007) provides even a more nuanced insight into this evolving process. As per this model, Pakistani English keeps on evolving its attributes due to the influence of Pakistan's native language; Urdu. The very similar perceptions are also found in the studies of researchers like Baumgardner (1993). Baumgardner (1993) emphasizes the discreteness of Pakistani English as it has its own lexical, syntactic, and phonological attributes.

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In the context Jenkins' (2003) work on English as a Lingua Franca, Pakistani English, with its peculiar attributes, conduce to the rich diversity of Englishes used internationally. A pluralistic approach towards understanding World Englishes has been advocated by Mahboob (2009). His work proposes that Pakistani English should be recognized as a linguistic variety, like other World Englishes, due to the functional and linguistic roles it plays in cultural and functional domains.

Mansoor (2004) highlights the challenges Pakistani English Language teachers encounter in finding convenient resources that encompass local linguistic nuances. Another major challenge is the Development of Contextual Materials that are not only linguistically broad but also contextually compatible to the students' cultural and societal heritage.

Parakrama (1995) and Higgins (2003) highlight the problematic attitudes towards non-standard Englishes like Pakistani English. It is evident from their research that how language is not just a medium of communication but also an identity marker. In nation like Pakistan, the position of Pakistani English becomes a subject of great importance.

A comprehensive understanding of complex dynamics that are surrounding the Pakistani english within the broader domain of World Englishes is provided in the previous discussion. Additionally, a consistent theme that is related to the challenges of integrating Pakistani English into the educational curriculum is also revealed through this literature. The need for a pedagogical shift towards the acceptance and integration of diverse Englishes; scholars like Canagarajah (1999) and Kirkpatrick (2007) in particular, into language teaching have emphasized Pakistani English.

The following study provides instrumental data on the perceptions of Pakistani English among English language teachers in Pakistan. The existing body of knowledge has been enriched by the more focused analysis into how these teachers perceive Pakistani English, what kind of challenges they encounter while its integration and the implications for their teaching practices. Moreover, this study delves deeper into the linguistic identity and educational policy in the context of World Englishes, particularly in post-colonial setting like Pakistan.

Thus on a whole, the literature review serves to establish a solid foundation for this study. It highlights the characteristics, evolution and global position of Pakistani

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English along with the pedagogical challenges that are associated with the use of Pakistani English in education. The background helps out in setting the stage for current research. It also aids in filling the identified gaps by delving deeper into the insights of English Language Teachers in Pakistan, thus enriching the discourse in language education and World Englishes.

Parakrama (1995) and Higgins (2003) highlight some problems towards non-standard English varieties by digging deeper into the challenges. Moreover, other studies like Mahmood's (2012) explore the diverse attitudes of teachers, students, and policymakers towards Pakistani English. Some people see it as a acknowledged variety of English while others take it as secondary or inferior version of English. Mansoor (2004) delves deeper into the tension between the localized variety of English and clinging to the standard form of it that is dominating in educational and professional domains.

Research Methodology

Research Design

A mixed method research design that is combining the qualitative insights collected through structured with the quantitative data collected through Likert-scale questionnaire is used in this study. Thus, a far-reaching understanding of the perceptions, challenges and the influence of those challenges on the perceptions of Pakistani English language teachers is obtained through this data.

The perceptions of teachers and the challenges they face are measured through Likert scale questionnaire, while a deeper insight into the thoughts and perceptions of Pakistani English language teachers has been obtained by the use of structured interviews.

Method of Data Collection

Population and Sample

The population selected for this study are seasoned Pakistani English language teachers. They are selected through the purposive sampling technique as they have significant experience in teaching Pakistani English. The sample includes 30 teachers for the questionnaire and a smaller, more focused group of 8 teachers for the in-depth interviews.

Tools of Data Collection

- **Likert Scale Questionnaire:** For the collection of quantitative data, an online questionnaire was developed, that consisted of statements rated on a 5-point Likert scale. This questionnaire was divided into three sections. Each of which was designed to address different aspects of the Pakistani university teachers' perceptions and challenges related to Pakistani English.
- **Structured Interviews:** Structured Interviews were conducted for the collection of data. Structured interviews were used in order to ensure the registration of flexibility in the responses and experiences of the teachers, along with ensuring consistency. Structured interviews helped getting diverse responses and opinions on the subject matter while not losing the course of the study.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

This study uses a blended theoretical framework that synergizes Zohrabi's "Strengthen the Validity of Evaluation Data and Findings" with Braj Kachru's "Three Circles Model of World Englishes" so as to provide a wholesome insight of Pakistani English from the perspectives of stakeholders; Pakistani English language teachers.

The theoretical framework "Strengthen the Validity of Evaluation Data and Findings" (Zohrabi, 2013, p. 258), emphasizes the importance of legitimacy in design as well as interpretation of research, specifically in language studies. The methodology is guided by this framework to ensure that the data collected is not only reliable and relevant but also accurately represents the perceptions and challenges of English Language Teachers in Pakistan regarding Pakistani English.

The framework of Zohrabi is conducive in shaping the mixed-method research design of this study. It high spots the demand of triangulating data from varying sources – the structured interviews and the Likert scale questionnaires– to complement the legitimacy of the findings. In order to make the conclusions far-reaching and comprehensive, the qualitative data is combined with the in-depth perceptions of Pakistani English language teacher, collected by structured interviews.

Another purpose served by this framework is the guidance of analytical process, so that any kind of preconceptions and misapprehensions are identified. This framework is particularly aligning with this study, as there are diverse educational, cultural and social backgrounds that may be a source of influencing the perceptions of

Pakistani English language teachers in Pakistan.

Another vital lens that helped in locating the Pakistani English in global context is the framework of Barat Kachru. The framework “Three Circles Model of World Englishes”, (Kachru. B, 1985, p. 110) becomes pertinent to this study. According to this model, English categorized into three circles. First is the Inner Circle which includes native language speaking countries, second circle is the Outer Circle which encompasses the countries where English is serving as second language due to its historical existence and third circle is the Expanding Circle having countries where English has the status of being used as an International language. As per this model, Pakistan lies in the outer circle, and thus it presents an exclusive interplay of English. It is influenced by local, historical and educational factors. The complex dynamics of Pakistani English such as defined features and diverse perceptions of English language teachers in Pakistan are explored with the help of this model.

Methods of Analysis

The alignment with Zohrabi's (2013) framework, a rigorous analytical approach is applied in this research to ensure the legitimacy of its findings:

- **Quantitative Analysis:** For analyzing the questionnaire data, Zohrabi's framework is followed and statistical methods are used. This statistical method provides a quantitative overview of teachers' perceptions along with test the legitimacy and reliability of the data. Other techniques that may include factor analysis is used to analyze and assess the constructs of the questionnaire. The application of this technique ensures the accurate measurement of predetermined aspects of perception and challenges.
- **Qualitative Analysis:** For the interpretation of interview data, Kachru's model becomes instrumental. This analysis aims to understand how Pakistani English, lying in the category of Outer Circle variety, is perceived by English language teachers in Pakistan. It is interpreted and analyzed in terms of its role, recognition, and acknowledgment both locally and internationally. It aims at exploring the teachers' detailed views on the cultural and linguistic importance of Pakistani English and the position it holds within the broad spectrum of World Englishes.

Underpinned by Zohrabi's and Kachru's framework , the integration of these methods offers a extensive and authentic analysis of the perceptions and challenges

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that are associated with Pakistani English among English Language Teachers in Pakistan.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table: *Quantitative Data*

Section	Statement	%	%	%
		Agreeing/Strongly Agreeing	Neutral	Disagreeing/Strongly Disagreeing
Perception of Pakistani English as a Global Variety				
1	Pakistani English as a significant international variety of English.	75%	11%	14%
2	I admit that Pakistani English has its own peculiar characteristics	83%	7%	10%
3	I consider Pakistani English an important linguistic variety for our students to learn.	79%	6%	15%

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Section	Statement	% Agreeing/Strongly Agreeing	% Neutral	% Disagreeing/Strongly Disagreeing
4	I consider Pakistani English as an acknowledged and legitimate variety of English.	69%	7%	24%
5	I perceive Pakistani English to be a recognized medium of communication in international contexts.	67%	7%	26%
Challenges in Integrating Pakistani English				
6	Use of teaching aids to assimilate Pakistani English features is a challenge for me.	73%	5%	22%
7	Challenges in	81%	8%	11%

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Section	Statement	% Agreeing/Strongly Agreeing	% Neutral	% Disagreeing/Strongly Disagreeing
	balancing the teaching of Pakistani English with standardized international English.			
8	Dealing with reluctance from students who prefer a more standardized form of English	65%	11%	24%
9	Finding befitting resources that aim at reflecting Pakistani English precisely	55%	21%	24%
10	Dealing with differing regional accents and dialects within Pakistani English	73%	11%	16%

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Section	Statement	% Agreeing/Strongly Agreeing	% Neutral	% Disagreeing/Strongly Disagreeing
Influence of Challenges on Perception				
11	I become less inclined to promote it because of the challenges I face in integrating Pakistani English.	59%	18%	23%
12	These challenges make me inclined towards appreciating the peculiarity of Pakistani English.	79%	9%	12%
13	Defeating these challenges enriches my perception of Pakistani English	73%	13%	14%
14	I perceive that addressing these	83%	9%	8%

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Section	Statement	% Agreeing/Strongly Agreeing	% Neutral	% Disagreeing/Strongly Disagreeing
15	challenges is important to the recognition of Pakistani English. The challenges in integrating Pakistani English have no effect on my perception of it.	56%	23%	21%

This table is designed to offer a clear representation of the teachers' perceptions, challenges and impact of those challenges on their perceptions about Pakistani English. It is presented through percentage in each of the category.

The data collected through the Likert scale questionnaire and structured interviews is presented and analyzed in this chapter. The purpose is to decode the perceptions and challenges as experienced by English Language Teachers in Pakistan regarding Pakistani English.

Presentation and Analysis of Quantitative Data (Likert Scale Questionnaire)

Perception of Pakistani English as a Global Variety by English Language Teachers

Statement 1: "Pakistani English as a significant international variety of English"

The percentage of 75% shows that a significant number of teachers tend to consider Pakistani English as an important variety playing its part on the global stage. This percentage suggests that there is a balanced to high level of agreement with this very statement.

- **Variability:** There lies 25% (11% neutral and 14% disagreeing) variability in responses, which shows that despite the general trend towards acceptance of the global importance of Pakistani English, there is still a variation of opinions among

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Pakistani English language teachers. Where some fully accept its importance, others show some kind of reservations that may be due to the influence by the global influence of well-established varieties of English such as American and British English.

Statement 2: "I admit that Pakistani English has its own peculiar characteristics"

One of the highest percentage in the survey that is 83% resolutely suggests that English language teachers in Pakistan extensively distinguish and acknowledge the peculiar characteristics of Pakistani English. This signals a vivid consensus on the particularity of this variety.

- **Variability:** As there lies a lower variability percentage (neutral 7% and Disagreement 10%) for this statement. It indicates that there is more homogeneity in teachers' perceptions. This homogeneity suggests a far-reaching acceptance of the peculiar phonological, lexical, and syntactic attributes that make Pakistani English a variety distinct from other varieties.

Statement 3: "I consider Pakistani English an important linguistic variety for our students to learn"

There lies a percentage of 79% for this statement, which presents a strong belief of English language teachers about the value of teaching Pakistani English to students. This percentage implies that the majority of teachers consider Pakistani English as an integral constituent of their students' language education.

Variability: The variability percentage of 17 (Neutral 6% & disagreeing 15%), although not as low as there was in Statement 2, yet implies a rationally high level of agreement among English language teachers. Nonetheless, this range in responses also serves as basis for implying that some teachers may have reservations. It can possibly be due to concerns about the global recognition of Pakistani English.

Statement 4: "I consider Pakistani English as an acknowledged and legitimate variety of English"

69% Pakistani English language teachers show agreement with statement and it signals a reasonably positive approach of the acknowledgment and legitimacy of Pakistani English among the teachers. This percentage pinpoints a acceptance, however not vigorously strong, of Pakistani English as an acknowledged variety of

English.

Variability: There lies a momentous disparity in perceptions among English language teachers, which is implied by the percentage of 31% (neutral 7% and 24 of disagreement). It is suggested by this variability that while there are many English language teachers who acknowledge Pakistani English as legitimate and authentic, there are still a number of teachers who may have doubts or reservations about Pakistani English. These reservations may probably be influenced by long-established views of language legitimacy that assist more established varieties like British or American English.

Statement 5: "I perceive Pakistani English to be a recognized medium of communication in international contexts"

A percentage of 67%, which lies on the lower side, propose a considerate viewpoint among Pakistani English language teachers towards the acceptability of Pakistani English in international contexts. It also indicates that there lies some hesitation in fully certifying Pakistani English as a globally communicable variety.

- **Variability:** As the variability, percentage (Neutral 7% & disagreement 26%) exists so it indicates that there are wide range of perceptions. It emphasizes the doubtfulness and dispute that surrounds the use of Pakistani English in international settings. This variation in perceptions might be the result of experiences, perceptions of global English norms, along with the perceived value of Pakistani English outside of Pakistani settings.

- **Interpretation and Implications**

Insightful revelations are provided by the analysis of these responses that are provided English Language Teachers in Pakistan about Pakistani English. These revelations suggest that there is a prevailing acceptance of the distinction and peculiarity of Pakistani English. Furthermore, its value is markedly acknowledged in the educational sector.

The variation, which is found in perception, can be ascribed to a large number of factors. It may encompass the educational background of teachers, their acknowledgment to various varieties of English, and the personal experiences they are having in English language teaching. Thus, this data underpins the demand for a more detailed understanding and discussion of Pakistani English, by considering Pakistani

English not just a local variant but also a vital component of the global tapestry of World Englishes.

Challenges in Integrating Pakistani English

Statement 6: "Use of teaching aids to assimilate Pakistani English features is a challenge for me"

With a percentage of 73%, this statement signals that it is somehow challenging Pakistani English language teachers to use teaching materials so that they could include features of Pakistani English. Thus, a need for recognition of such adaptation is suggested along with the difficulties involved.

Variability: A variability percentage of (neutral 5% & disagreement 22%) suggests that although this challenge is widely accepted, but there may occur a variation in experiences of English language teachers. This variability can be the result of factors like the accessibility of resources, support of institution, along with the proficiency and understanding of Pakistani English among Pakistani English language teachers.

Statement 7: "Challenges in balancing the teaching of Pakistani English with standardized international English"

The percentage of 81% shows that these is a considerable number of English language teachers who find it difficult to balance the teaching of Pakistani English with standardized forms of international English. A prevailing effort among teachers to maneuver between these two linguistic realms is indicated through this percentage.

Variability: The variability percentage of (Neutral 8% and disagreement 11%), along with proposing some level of consent, also proposes that there might occur differences in experiences of English language teachers. These differences may probably be based on their teaching contexts and personal opinion about the role of Pakistani English in education.

Statement 8: "Dealing with reluctance from students who prefer a more standardized form of English"

A 65% of agreement of Pakistani English language teachers with this statement indicates that due to the students who favor internationally recognized and standard varieties of English, a frequent resistance is encountered. This resistance leads to a considerable challenge in the classroom.

Variability: Along with that, the higher variability percentage (Neutral 11% &

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disagreement 24%) suggests the varying experiences among English language teachers. These varying experiences can be due to the impact of students' backgrounds, will, and liability to other English forms that are standard ones.

Statement 9: "Finding befitting resources that aim at reflecting Pakistani English precisely"

The agreement percentage of 55 for this statement reveals that English language teachers in approaching resources that could precisely represent Pakistani English encounter a significant challenge. This percentage suggests that there lies a prominent gap in the accessibility of these resources.

Variability: A variability percentage of (Neutral 21 & disagreement 24) signals a wide range of experiences. These experiences are likely to be effected by factors such as support of relevant institution, geographical location, and availability of resource.

Statement 10: "Dealing with the differing regional accents and dialects within Pakistani English"

73% agreement of Pakistani English language teachers suggests that it is generally found difficult to cater the varying regional dialects and accents within Pakistani English. This percentage shows that within Pakistan there is an awareness of the linguistic diversity and the effect it has on English language teaching.

- **Variability:** The variability percentage of (neutral 11 & 16% disagreement) pinpoints a diversity of experiences among English language teachers in supervising this variety. This diversity could be an effect of factors like the diversity of the students in terms of their region, linguistic backgrounds that English language teachers possess, and the experience they have in teaching varying groups.

- **Interpretation and Implications**

Two key challenges are being highlighted in the assimilation of Pakistani English into educational practices: first, is the usage of teaching materials and second is the balancing of local and international varieties of English. Another challenge that is related to adaptation of resource indicates a broader issue in Pakistani English language education materials development, where there is often an underrepresentation of local varieties. Hence, it is suggested by this gap that there is a need for a concerted effort in the domain of developing teaching resources that are comprehensive of Pakistani EnglishAs, there lies difficulty in balancing Pakistani

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English with standardized international English, thus a profound pedagogical and ideological challenge is reflected through it. Some important questions related to the goals of English language education in Pakistan are raised, like, should global intelligibility or local relevance be the focus, or a combination of both? \

- **Influence of Challenges on Perception**

Statement 11: "I become less inclined to promote it because of the challenges I face in integrating Pakistani English"

- A limited tendency among some teachers to be less inclined in promoting Pakistani English due to the challenges they encounter in its integration are indicated by the percentage of 59. This percentage serves the purpose of indicating a certain level of unwillingness or hesitance. These reluctances possibly be the result of difficulties faced in teaching Pakistani English variety.

- **Variability:** An apparent diversity in perceptions among Pakistani English Language teachers is found by the higher variability percentage of (Neutral 18% & disagreement 23). It signals the discouragement faced by some teachers due to these challenges. While others may not compulsorily find these challenges as a hindrance in promoting Pakistani English.

Statement 12: "These challenges make me inclined towards appreciating the peculiarity of Pakistani English"

For this statement, 79% Pakistani English language teachers show their agreement. This percentage suggests that a significant number of teachers actually come to appreciate the peculiarity of Pakistani English. This may be the result of the challenges encountered by them while teaching Pakistani English. A positive effect of the difficulties encountered is indicated by this percentage.

- **Variability:** Some disagreement of (Neutral 9% & disagreement 12%) is also indicated by responses. This variability shows a comparatively strong consensus among Pakistani English language teachers related to the appreciation of the peculiar features of Pakistani English.

Statement 13: "Defeating these challenges enriches my perception of Pakistani English"

73% agreement with this statement shows that many Pakistani English language teachers feel that if the challenges that are associated with integrating Pakistani

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English are overthrown then it may positively influences the Pakistani English language teachers' perception of this linguistic variety. It is also signaled that navigating through these challenges may lead to an affirmative view of Pakistani English.

- **Variability:** A variability percentage of (Neutral 13% & 14% disagreement) shows a moderate level of agreement among Pakistani English language teachers, yet some diversity in experiences and perceptions is still there. Therefore, it is suggested that while many Pakistani English Language teachers find overcoming these challenges beneficial, yet the degree to which this influences their perceptions can vary.

Statement 14: "I perceive that addressing these challenges is important to the recognition of Pakistani English"

The agreement percentage of 83, one of the highest in the survey, strongly signals that teachers intensely believe that if these challenges were addressed in teaching Pakistani English, then it would significantly be helpful for its wider recognition. This percentage indicates a harmony on the importance of overcoming these challenges.

- **Variability:** The comparatively low variability percentage (Neutral 9% & disagreement 10%) in case of this statement suggests that there is a high level of agreement among teachers about the critical nature of this issue. This highlights that most teachers perceive that there is a link between addressing teaching challenges related to Pakistani English and raising the acceptance of Pakistani English.

Statement 15: "The challenges in integrating Pakistani English have no effect on my perception of it"

A relatively low percentage of 56 indicates that for most teachers, in integrating Pakistani English, these challenges do indeed have influence on their perception of this linguistic variety. This lower percentage also implies that English language teachers' views on Pakistani English are not **free** from the practical challenges they face in teaching it.

- **Variability:** A range of responses is highlighted by the variability percentage of (Neutral 23% and disagreement 21%). This signals the fact that although most Pakistani English language teachers are influenced by these challenges yet there is a variation in it. Where many of the teachers are strongly influenced by these challenges,

some may not find their perceptions significantly influenced by these challenges.

- **Interpretation and Implications**

A complex relationship between the challenges in integrating Pakistani English and its influence on the teachers' perception is provided by the worthy insights of Pakistani English language teachers. There also lies a recognition of overcoming these challenges for the wider recognition of Pakistani English in World Englishes. This analysis also aims at providing evidence that there is a need for complementary environment that could endue Pakistani English language teachers towards integrating Pakistani English into their teaching. As this complementary environment would be helpful in providing the Pakistani English language teachers with appropriate teaching materials and professional development opportunities, so it would be helpful in enriching the Pakistani English language teachers' perceptions and skills as well.

Presentation and Analysis of Qualitative Data (Structured Interviews)

Introduction

Pakistani English Language Teachers are interviewed via structured interviews and the qualitatively gathered data offers in-depth knowledge of their perceptions about Pakistani English's status and challenges that are faced by them while teaching. Barat Kachru's Three Circle Model is used for the analysis of qualitative data. 8 teachers were interviewed for the collection of this data.

Data & Analysis

- **Status of Pakistani English:**

Perceptions of Pakistani teachers regarding Pakistani English and its status differed widely. Many teachers favoured the growing importance of Pakistani English and it as a different variety of English, which reflected the linguistic diversity and Pakistan's cultural. One teacher revealed, "Pakistani English is not only a dialect; it is a mode through which our identity and culture are demonstrated." This statement unveils the belief that Pakistani English is more than a tool of communication; it represents the national identity.

However, few teachers showed concerns about the global recognition it and its acceptance. Another teacher spoke, "we know its value locally, I'm not sure if it's recognized globally, which can be a matter for our learners' future goals."

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- **Challenges in Teaching Pakistani English:**

The considerations and involvement of Pakistani English in the curriculum caused many challenges. Lack of adequate teaching material was a common thing. "It was challenging to find textbooks and resources that correctly reflect Pakistani English. We most of the time need to rely on resources based on British or American English," shared by one teacher while highlighting the resource gap.

Another challenge was to keeping balance in Pakistani English and standardized English varieties. A teacher revealed, "We're constantly struggling between teaching the local variety and the so-called 'international' English. It's hard to keep the right balance without undermining one variety over the other or confusing the students."

- **Pedagogical Strategies and Responses of the Students:**

Pakistani Teachers use distinct strategies to meet these challenges. Few focused on comparative studies while highlighting similarities and differences between standard and Pakistani English varieties. Others stressed the language's functional aspects where English teaching as communication tool rather than as a couple of rigid rules.

There were mixed responses of students regarding learning of Pakistani English. While some learners acknowledged learning a version of Pakistani English related to their linguistic reality, others, especially those seeking for international opportunities, showed no acknowledgement. "Few students question the benefit of learning Pakistani English because they worry about it by thinking it might not be as useful internationally," a teacher responded.

- **Navigating Linguistic Diversity:**

A significantly challenging aspect responded by teachers was the Pakistan's linguistic diversity. Teachers are often required to navigate between different regional dialects and English accents, which instills complexity to their teaching. "Each Pakistani region has its own way of English speaking. As an instructor, I need to be mindful of these changes and making sure that my teaching is inclusive," responded one educator.

Influence on Teaching Methods and Student Response

- **Diverse Classroom Dynamics and Teacher Adaptations:** The data uncovers particularized variations in dynamics of classroom in various regions and types of schools. For example, in urban private schools, instructor revealed a more positive

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student response for Pakistani English, referring the higher level of experience of diverse English varieties. Conversely, in few government schools, particularly in rural areas, there was a remarkable preference for traditional English forms, considered as more respectful. Pakistani educators in these settings often find themselves favoring the relevance to Pakistani English.

- **Creative Engagement Techniques:** Some teachers left the traditional methods and using role-playing and talk to put light on the use of Pakistani English in daily situations. One educator responded, "Role-playing regarding local scenes permits learners to use Pakistani English naturally to make the lessons more enjoyable."
- **Student Reactions and Perceptions:** A significant observation was that students who had relatives abroad or aspirations for international education were more likely to question the utility of Pakistani English.
- **Analysis**
- **Socio-cultural and Economic Factors:** The analysis reveals that students' responses are deeply impacted by their economic and socio-cultural backgrounds. Students from more rich, globally known backgrounds tend to display skepticism regarding Pakistani English, as they associate it with local bounds rather than international opportunities.
- **Future of Pakistani English in Education:** In Education, there are profound long-term implications for Pakistani English. These could range from slight moves in language policies to alterations in training of teachers and designs of curriculum, potentially going to a more representative and inclusive approach to teaching of English language in Pakistan.

It demonstrates the need for a culturally sensitive and adaptive approach in English teaching, keeping in mind the students' various socio-economic backgrounds.

Role of Regional Diversity and Perception Changes

- **Data & Quotes**
- **Several Regional Influences on Teaching:** Instructors from diverse regions shared their new experiences. A teacher in Karachi mentioned, "My pupils mostly use Urdu idioms which are directly translated to English. I use these examples to talk about the beauty of linguistic mix in Pakistani English." Another teacher from the

northern areas answered, "Learners here mix Pashto structures with their English speech. We explore these blends as components of our lessons by celebrating linguistic diversity."

- **Dynamic Perceptions and Approaches of Pakistani English language teachers:** An insightful attitude by one of the teachers with the experience of two decades is reflected in his statement, "Though the variety which I was exposed to, being student was British English but I now acknowledge the legitimacy of our linguistic variety as it is our identity." A teacher from Lahore quoted that previously he was considering Pakistani English an alteration from standard one but I, know fully admit to the fact that it is an authentic variety which is reflecting our culture, so we must promote it.

- **Analysis**

- **Impact of Regional Variations on Pakistani English Language Education:** There is a huge impact of regional linguistic on Pakistani English which is highlighted through this data analysis. The cultural context and real-life relevance into the classroom setting enriches Pakistani English language education. The need for teachers' acknowledgment and more specifically, the utilization of this linguistic variant is also emphasized by this analysis.

- **Teachers as Catalysts for Linguistic Acceptance:** It is very important for Pakistani English language teachers that they keep evolving their perceptions towards Pakistani English as they are catalysts for the acceptance of this linguistic variety. When they would start perceiving it as a deviation and recognize it as a valid linguistic variety, then they would contribute in the global acceptance and recognition of Pakistani English as a linguistic variety.

As regional diversity plays a significant role in framing and shaping the perceptions of Pakistani English among Pakistani English language teachers. Thus it has been, in detailed, analyzed in 4.2.3. This section highlights the changing power of Pakistani English language teachers in redesigning and reshaping the linguistic norms and ultimately the significance of assimilating regional linguistic influences into English language curriculum.

Synthesis of Data

Assimilation of quantitative data with qualitative data provides a nuanced

understanding of the perceptions of Pakistani English language teachers along with the role of Pakistani English in education. As the quantitative data provides numerically precise data about the levels of agreement and disagreement among Pakistani English language teachers, while qualitative data adds to the richness of insights into the personal experiences and perceptions of Pakistani English teachers.

- **Major Themes and Trends:**
- **Perceptions of Pakistani English:** Qualitative data further elucidates the positive perceptions of Pakistani English language teachers that were previously indicated by the quantitative data. Pakistani English language teachers often incline towards celebrating the peculiarity and cultural sonority of Pakistani English. Nonetheless, qualitative and quantitative data sets also imply that there are certain concerns about its international recognition which leads to an ever increasing tension between its local relevance along with international status of it.
- **Challenges in Integrating Pakistani English:** From adaptation of relevant and innovative resources to addressing students' varying attitudes towards Pakistani English, several challenges faced by Pakistani English language teachers are highlighted by this synthesis. These challenges include not only the organizational but also the educational challenges and demand from the teacher to tailor the complicated linguistic and cultural landscape.
- **Vigorous Teaching Practices:** These challenges catch varying and dynamic responses of Pakistani English language teachers. While some of them have inclined themselves towards the adaptation of innovative methods in integrating Pakistani English, others are reluctant and they call for some type of structured resources. This diversity in responses shows that there lies diversity in extensive educational landscape's resilience and adaptability.
- **Student Engagement and Perspectives:** As the analysis presents some mixed responses from students, so an extensive conversation about language and identity is highlighted. These attitudes from students about Pakistani English reflects their linguistic and cultural backgrounds. Thus, on a whole, a deeper and nuanced argument about how language shapes personal and collective identities is revealed through these attitudes.

Findings, Conclusion, and Recommendations

Findings

A nuanced insight into the perceptions, challenges and implications, associated with the Pakistani English among Pakistani English language teachers, is provided by the research. This wholesome insight is gained from a synthesis of the quantitative and qualitative data which is collected through the Likert scale questionnaire and structured interviews.

1. **Perceptions of Pakistani English:** In lieu of Kachru's Outer Circle classification, the study unveils that there exist complex and varied perceptions of Pakistani among Pakistani English language teachers. They admit its peculiarity, which is influenced, by Pakistani cultural and Linguistics contexts. Nonetheless, there is an apparent disparity in views concerning its international recognition and legitimacy, representing the current argument within the Outer Circle nations on the status of their English varieties.

2. **Challenges in Teaching Pakistani English:** The findings high spot the teaching challenges that Pakistani English language teachers face in integrating Pakistani English into their studies. A main challenge in it is to balance the instruction of Pakistani English with internationally recognized varieties of English, along with the adaptation of teaching resource that could appropriately reflect its peculiar features. These challenges signal the wider scenario in the Outer circle, where there is coexistence of local English forms with international English paradigm.

3. **Influence of Theoretical Frameworks on Interpreting Perceptions:** A methodologically vigorous study of teachers' perceptions, is ensured by Zohrabi's framework, while Kachru's model helps in contextualizing these perceptions within the extensive discourse of World Englishes. The use of these models is helpful in describing the diverse attitudes of Pakistani English language teachers towards Pakistani English. These attitudes range from its defined and distinct identity to the concerns of its international usage.

4. **Implications for Teaching Practices:** This study highlights that there is a need for bringing innovation in the teaching approaches related to Pakistani English. As Pakistani English language teachers are piloting a complex field, where they have to encounter with the unique features of Pakistani English, so they must equip

themselves with the linguistic skills that are necessary for the global communication. The crux of the findings is that the compounded framework of Zohrabi and Kachru provide a nuanced insight into the perceptions and challenges that the Pakistani English language teacher encounter. The evolving nature of Pakistani English along with its peculiar features and attributes and the continued quest for global recognition is also highlighted.

Conclusion

The conclusions of this study are a reflection of nuanced analysis of qualitative and quantitative data, which are providing a deep insight into the legitimacy and recognition of Pakistani English within the larger domain of World Englishes.

- **Authenticity and recognition of Pakistani English:**

It can be concluded, after the detailed analysis of this study that Pakistani English still has to face many challenges and difficulties despite it has its own distinctive and peculiar attributes. Despite of its relevance with the local context, it is facing challenges in its acceptance as a legitimate global variety.

- **Challenges in Teaching Pakistani English:**

Pakistani English language teachers, while integrating Pakistani English into their teaching also face many challenges. These challenges may include the balance with the standardized forms of English students' reluctance towards it, and the providence of appropriate teaching resources.

- **Impact of Teaching Practices on Student Engagement:**

It has also been revealed by this study that if innovative teaching practices are used in Pakistani English then the students' engagement can increase up to significant levels.

Recommendations

This extensive study also leads to several recommendations which are;

- **Codification of Pakistani English:**

Improved positive perceptions of Pakistani English owe to the development of Pakistani English. Development of Pakistani English urges Pakistani English Linguists to focus certain efforts on key language areas i.e. Morphology, Phonology, Syntax and Semantics. There is a dire need to study the structures of Pakistani English leading to developing a grammar for Pakistani English. The only way Pakistani English can have a better perception internally and externally is through a proper

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codification. It would bring Pakistani English a global recognition. That in turn, would also nullify the reservations that Pakistani Language Teacher have about Pakistani English as Language Variety.

- **Inclusive Curriculum Design:**

In order to balance Pakistani English with Standard forms of English, an inclusive curriculum must be designed. The development of such curriculum would aid in preparing students for communication in local and global contexts.

- **Resource Creation:**

Special focus must be paid towards the development of such teaching materials that could efficiently reflect the nuances of Pakistani English. These resources may include textbooks, multimedia resources and adequate reading material displaying the Pakistani English in legitimate contexts.

- **Further Empirical Research:**

Further research, aiming at exploration of the perceptions of various stakeholder such as parents, policy maker and specifically students, about Pakistani English must be encouraged. Moreover, studies should be conducted on comparison of Pakistani English with other varieties of English. Such studies would be helpful in integration of Pakistani English in global settings.

- **Societal Attitudes and Student Engagement:**

Efforts towards changing the perceptions of societies, educational stakeholders and policymaker towards Pakistani English should also encouraged. Certain strategies should also be developed to increase students' interest in Pakistani English. Students' inclination towards the usage of Pakistani English would bring significant change. That is how; Pakistani English would be awarded global recognition.

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